

BATSS

NEWSLETTER #2 - MARCH 2025

Welcome back to the BATSS community

As we continue developing safer, more efficient, and more sustainable **battery systems for transport and mobile applications**, we're excited to share our latest updates and achievements with you!

In this issue we explore the details of our thermal and electrical **innovations** and reflect on our participation in key **industry events** as well as our latest **consortium meeting**. We also take a look ahead at an upcoming workshop from one of our clustered projects and share highlights from other **clustered partners and activities**.

Enjoy reading!

INNOVATION

Take a closer look at our battery system's thermal design.

[Learn more](#)

Discover the cutting-edge **electrical innovations** of our technology.

[Learn more](#)

INDUSTRY EVENTS

At the **RTR2025**, BATSS took the stage as part of the '*High-performance and safe-by-design next-generation battery systems for road transport applications*' session, alongside fellow projects from the EU-INGENIOuS cluster.

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BATSS was at the **BID2024** as part of the EU-INGENIOuS stand, featuring groundbreaking European battery projects dedicated to driving innovation and collaboration in the sector.

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BATSS participated in the **Batteries Event 2024**, meeting key stakeholders, experts, and decision-makers from across the entire battery value chain.

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Everything about our General Assembly in Lyon last December.

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CLUSTERING NEWS

BATSS participated in a collaborative meeting with **EGVIAfor2Zero, BEPA, and JRC**, as part of their annual meeting on next-generation battery technologies, testing, and sustainability.

[Learn more](#)

BATSS was at the **EARPA Autumn Meeting 2024**, with other professionals involved in European projects and proposals in the automotive and road mobility sectors.

InnoBMS will host its first **Advisory Board (AB) workshop** on 13 May 2025, showcasing their first results including their BMS architecture requirements and use cases, data management protocol and BMS E/E layout for implementation.

The workshop is only open for AB members. If you are interested to learn more and join their AB, please contact a.rvdh@uniresearch.com.

Find BATSS listed in the **EARPA project repository**, the section with an overview of some of the EU-funded projects in which EARPA members are involved!

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